

SOME ETHICAL PROBLEMS WITH THE 150-SEMESTER HOUR ACCOUNTING EDUCATION REQUIREMENT

Robert W. McGee¹

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Abstract

Both proponents and opponents of the 150 semester-hour accounting education requirement have used utilitarian arguments to justify their position. This paper takes a different approach. It begins with a brief review of the utilitarian arguments that have been made regarding the 150 semester-hour requirement, then proceeds to apply rights theory to the question. The paper concludes that the 150 semester-hour requirement is a bad idea because it violates rights.

Introduction

In January 1988 the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA) amended its bylaws to require (new) members to have 150 semester hours of college education by the year 2000.² This action was the response to some AICPA

¹ Seton Hall University. An earlier version of this paper was presented at the Northeast Business & Economics Association 1997 Annual Conference, Philadelphia, PA, September 26-27, 1997. I would like to thank the two anonymous reviewers and the participants at this conference who offered their suggestions for improvement. The author can be reached at bob@dumontinst.com.

² Priscilla M. Austin and Daniel J. O'Mara, *Prime Time: An Evaluation of the 150-Semester Hour Educational Requirement*, PENNSYLVANIA CPA J. 18-21 (Fall 1989), at 18.

committees that had recommended five years of education as being the minimum acceptable for accountants because of the increasing complexity of the accounting profession.³ Since then, the AICPA and its sister organizations in the various states have been lobbying their respective legislatures to adopt a 150-semester hour requirement to take the CPA exam.⁴

There is nothing wrong with a professional association making whatever conditions it wants as a requirement of membership. Ethical problems arise, however, when private organizations lobby the government to adopt their membership requirements into law. That is what is happening in this case, since the AICPA and its supporters would prevent individuals from practicing as certified public accountants unless they have completed 150 semester hours of college coursework.

There are a number of reasons why the AICPA's proposed 150 semester-hour accounting requirement would be harmful, both to the general public and to the profession itself. Those who have argued in favor of the requirement have argued from a utilitarian position -- the greatest good for the greatest number, or the good outweighs the bad or the winners exceed the losers (positive-sum game).⁵ Those who have criticized the requirement have also based

³ ROBERT H. ROY AND JAMES H. MACNEILL, HORIZONS FOR A PROFESSION (1967); *Report of the Committee on Education and Experience Requirements for CPAs*, AICPA, 1967; *Restructuring Professional Standards to Achieve Professional Excellence in a Changing Environment*, AICPA, 1986.

⁴ The battle to pass this requirement in New Jersey took place in 1995. See *The Case Against the 150 Semester-Hour Requirement for CPAs*, testimony given by Robert W. McGee before the Senate Commerce Committee, Trenton, New Jersey, May 15, 1995, reprinted in POLICY ANALYSIS NO. 25, July 1996, The Dumont Institute for Public Policy Research.

⁵ For a detailed and favorable exposition of utilitarian ethics, see WILLIAM H. SHAW, CONTEMPORARY ETHICS: TAKING ACCOUNT OF UTILITARIANISM (1999). For criticisms of the utilitarian approach to ethics, see Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in the Methodology of Law & Economics*, COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS 209-223 (1997); Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in NAFTA, GATT and All Other Trade Agreements*, 14 NW J. INT'L L. & BUS. 549-565 (1994).

their arguments almost exclusively on utilitarian reasoning -- the harm caused by the requirement exceeds the benefits. The reason why two opposing sides to this argument -- or any argument for that matter -- can take utilitarian positions is because there is no way to precisely measure benefits and harms. One must merely estimate who is affected -- both positively and negatively -- and by how much. That is the fatal flaw in basing an argument on utilitarian theory. Another flaw in limiting oneself to utilitarian arguments is that rights are totally ignored. Yet rights theory is a better approach to use if one is concerned with the ethical aspects of policy.

This paper takes a different approach than those that are based on utilitarian arguments. It begins with a brief review of the utilitarian arguments that have been made regarding the 150 semester-hour requirement, then proceeds to apply rights theory to the question. The paper concludes that the 150 semester-hour requirement is a bad idea because it violates rights.

UTILITARIAN ARGUMENTS

Here are brief summaries of the main utilitarian arguments that have been used to argue that the 150 semester-hour requirement is bad.⁶

Reduced Enrollment in Accounting Programs

Adding a fifth year to accounting programs would reduce

⁶ Some of these arguments were discussed in Robert W. McGee, *The Economics and Ethics of Requiring 150 Semester Hours of Coursework to Sit for the CPA Exam*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY 310-314 (Spring 1998); Austin and O'Mara, *supra*; Larry Deppe, Don R. Hansen and Stan Jenne, *The 150-Hour Educational Requirement: The History and Message of the Utah Experience*, 2 ACCOUNTING HORIZONS 53-57 (June 1988); Paul Clolery, *The Debate Intensifies over the 150-Hour Rule*, 25 THE PRACTICAL ACCOUNTANT 74-80 (December 1992); David J. Ortinau, Terry J. Engle and Jerry D. Siebel, *Attitudinal Insights into the Costs and Benefits of a Mandated Postbaccalaureate Education Requirement*, 3 ACCOUNTING HORIZONS 86-94 (March 1989).

the number of accounting majors. Choosing accounting as a major would become 25% more costly than choosing another business major because it would take five years to complete instead of four. A survey of more than 25,000 CPA candidates found that the accounting profession would suffer a 44% decrease in the number of students who would choose accounting as a profession if the 150 hour law were in effect in their state.

Fewer CPAs in the Future

Fewer accounting majors today means fewer CPAs in the future. In three states that have implemented the 150-hour requirement, the number of new CPAs has dropped by about one third. In Florida, first-time applicants for the CPA exam dropped by 59% between 1980 (4 years before the 150 hour law was implemented) and 1992, despite a 38% increase in population over the same time period.

Reduced Demand for Accounting Professors

If the number of accounting majors decreases, there will be less demand for accounting professors. Colleges and universities will have to lay off accounting faculty.⁷

⁷ Interestingly enough, accounting faculties have been among the greatest proponents of the 150-semester hour requirement. When the author has asked various accounting professors why they support the 150 semester-hour requirement, the common response is that the requirement is in the public interest. They also think that it will boost enrollment in their master's degree programs (which is purely self-serving). If they really wanted to serve their own interests, they would lobby to reduce the liberal arts requirement, which prevents students from taking even more accounting courses. Yet the professorate continues to pay homage to the alleged benefits of a liberal arts education. When asked to list the benefits of such an education, they are usually hard pressed to come up with any benefits other than the usual claptrap about broadening one's education. Why not let the market (students) decide by dropping the liberal arts requirement and letting them take whatever classes they want? If they place value on liberal arts education they will take even more liberal arts courses than is presently required. The counter argument, that professors know what is best for students, smacks of elitism as well as disrespect for the market process.

Reduction in the Number of Accounting Programs

Colleges and universities that presently have small accounting programs may decide to drop their programs rather than offer a 150 hour program,⁸ thus making accounting education less available to residents of the states that adopt the 150 semester-hour rule.

Higher Costs To Consumers

Unless the demand for accounting services decreases, fewer accountants and CPAs means higher costs for anyone who uses accounting services, without correspondingly higher benefits. Not only would CPAs cost more, but non-CPA accounting services would also cost more because of the decreased number of accounting majors that colleges and universities would be turning out.

Higher Cost To Taxpayers

Tuition covers only part of the cost of a college education. Taxpayers pay a substantial portion of the total costs of state colleges and universities.⁹ One study estimated that adding a fifth year to the accounting education requirement would cost New Jersey taxpayers an extra \$4.5 million annually. Other studies, if they were conducted, would likely arrive at additional cost figures

⁸ THE 150 HOUR LAW: UNNECESSARY RESTRICTION ON THE CERTIFIED PUBLIC ACCOUNTANT (CPA) PROFESSION, American Legislative Exchange Council, Washington, DC, Vol. 20, No. 10, November 1994, p. 3. The National Association of State Boards of Accountancy and the AICPA sharply disagreed with the contents of this paper. For a summary of their criticism, see *AICPA and NASBA Presidents Set the Record Straight on 150-Hour Education Requirement*, 179 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTANCY 19-20 (June 1995). The arguments on both sides were utilitarian based.

⁹ It is not at all clear why some individuals should be forced to pay for the education of others. For a discussion of this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Brown v. Board of Education: Forty Years of Asking the Wrong Question & the Case for Privatization of Education*, ST. LOUIS UNIVERSITY PUBLIC LAW REVIEW (1999).

for other states.

Businesses Would Be Less Competitive

If businesses in a state that has adopted the 150 semester-hour requirement have to pay more for accounting services than businesses in other states, they will be at a competitive disadvantage. One might argue that the extra knowledge the CPAs in these states possess is worth something, and that factor needs to be considered. However, the AICPA and the other groups that are pushing for the additional education would not require any additional accounting courses. They want accounting students to take more liberal arts courses. Thus, it appears that the extra knowledge that students would acquire would be of much benefit to the companies that hire them.

Disparate Impact on Minorities and the Poor

Requiring 150 semester-hours to sit for the CPA exam would have a disparate impact on minorities and the poor, since these groups are least able to afford a fifth year of college education. Universities that are trying to recruit more minorities into the accounting profession would find recruitment more difficult.

No Increase in Quality

The proposed 150-hour law would not require any additional accounting courses. The requirement could be met by taking an additional year of liberal arts courses, which does nothing to improve an accountant's competence to practice accounting. The public would not be any better protected by adding a fifth year. One might argue (as did one of the anonymous referees) that liberal arts does add something and that the intense, technical nature of an accounting education needs to be balanced with liberal arts to prevent accounting professionals from graduating with no vision. The weakness in this argument is that accounting majors already have to take twice as many liberal arts courses as accounting courses -- 50% compared to 25%. It is not at

all clear how anyone can say that they are being deprived of liberal arts courses. It also is not clear how one can get "vision" by taking more liberal arts courses, especially when the professors who teach these courses are almost always antibusiness in orientation.

No Market Demand for a Fifth Year

A study by the President's Council on Integrity and Efficiency found that entry-level auditors with just a bachelor's degree received higher ratings than those with additional education. A study funded by the Institute of Management Accountants and the Financial Executives Institute and partly assisted by the AICPA found that less than 3% of corporate employers prefer job applicants who have a master's degree for accounting positions.¹⁰ Those who would like their employees to receive additional education prefer that they receive post-baccalaureate education after they have started to work. More than 90% of the respondents to the IMA/FEI study said that the specific courses an entry-level accountant took is more important than the number of credits the applicant has earned beyond the bachelor's degree. A survey of CPAs in California, Illinois and New York found that CPAs are generally satisfied with accounting students' current technical education.¹¹

Other Utilitarian Arguments

If colleges and universities are not adequately preparing accountants for entry-level positions, it does not follow that adding a fifth year -- and increasing the cost of a college education by 25% -- is the solution. There may be other, less costly solutions,

¹⁰ WHAT CORPORATE AMERICA WANTS IN ENTRY-LEVEL ACCOUNTANTS, A Joint Research Project of The Institute of Management Accountants and The Financial Executives Institute, August 1994.

¹¹ *Journal of Accountancy*, September 1992. In all fairness, it must be mentioned that the firms that hire accounting graduates are generally dissatisfied with the extent of writing and critical thinking skills that recent graduates have. It is unclear how these deficiencies can be removed by adding a fifth year of education, however. What have they been learning in the first four years?

such as:

- Hiring professors who have real-world experience.¹² Many colleges and universities prefer to hire PhDs with little or no real-world experience rather than experienced practitioners who have only a masters degree and professional certification.¹³ The quality of accounting education might be improved if the emphasis is shifted to favor professors who have actually practiced what they are teaching.
- Cutting back on liberal arts requirements, so that students can spend more time studying accounting.¹⁴
- Placing more emphasis on communication skills within the liberal arts component of the curriculum.

These are all issues that colleges and universities must decide for themselves. It is a poor idea to legislate accounting education requirements, since the result would be a one-size-fits-all system that may be worse than the current one. If colleges and universities are given the flexibility to try different approaches to

¹² For a discussion of this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Let's Have an Experience Requirement for Accounting Educators: An Economic & Ethical Analysis*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Summer 1998).

¹³ A strong case can be made that a PhD should not be required to teach in a college or university. For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Do Accounting Educators Need a PhD? A Look at Some Neglected Economic and Ethical Issues*, 2 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Spring 1999).

¹⁴ For an economic analysis of the undesirability of the liberal arts requirement for accountants, see Robert W. McGee, *Suboptimization in Accounting Education and the Subjective Theory of Value: Some Suggestions for Change*, 2 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Winter 1999). For a rebuttal, see Mark C. Mitschow, *Suboptimization in Accounting Education: A Rebuttal*, 2 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Winter 1999). For a rejoinder to Mitschow, see Robert W. McGee, *Suboptimization in Accounting Education and the Subjective Theory of Value: A Rejoinder*, 2 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Winter 1999).

accounting education, the better approaches will eventually win out over the weaker ones.

Another issue, one that is not often addressed, is whether the present CPA exam does a good job of measuring accounting competence.¹⁵ Assuming for the sake of argument that those who can pass the CPA exam *do* have good accounting skills, a relevant question to ask is whether there should be *any* education requirement to take the CPA exam. After all, those who have not attained the desired competency level will fail regardless of how many courses they have taken. Why not abolish all education requirements and give everyone the opportunity to take the CPA

¹⁵ Another, more basic issue is whether only CPAs should be allowed to audit financial statements. Government grants this monopoly to certified public accountants, supposedly to protect the public interest. However, the literature on monopoly over the last few decades clearly indicates that the vast majority of antitrust laws and lawsuits serve to protect the vested special interests at the expense of the general public. Monopolies of any kind tend to result in higher prices and reduced quality than would exist in a market where all service providers are free to offer their services to the public. A good research topic would be to apply monopoly theory to CPAs to see if the CPA profession is an exception to the general rule that antitrust laws work against the public interest. For more on how antitrust laws serve special interests at the expense of the general public, see D.T. ARMENTANO, *ANTITRUST POLICY: THE CASE FOR REPEAL* (1986); D.T. ARMENTANO, *THE MYTHS OF ANTITRUST: ECONOMIC THEORY AND LEGAL CASES* (1972); DOMINICK T. ARMENTANO, *ANTITRUST AND MONOPOLY: ANATOMY OF A POLICY FAILURE* (2ND ED. 1990); WILLIAM F. SHUGHART II, *ANTITRUST POLICY AND INTEREST-GROUP POLITICS* (1990); YALE BROZEN, *IS GOVERNMENT THE SOURCE OF MONOPOLY? AND OTHER ESSAYS*, Cato Institute (1980); William F. Shughart II, *Don't Revise the Clayton Act, Scrap It!* 6 *CATO J.* 925-932 (Winter 1987); Walter Block, *Total Repeal of Antitrust Legislation: A Critique of Bork, Brozen, and Posner*, 8 *REV. AUSTRIAN ECON.* 35-70 (1994); Thomas J. DiLorenzo, *The Myth of Natural Monopoly*, 9 *REV. AUSTRIAN ECON.* 43-58 (1996); Donald J. Boudreaux and Thomas J. DiLorenzo, *The Protectionist Roots of Antitrust*, 6 *REV. AUSTRIAN ECON.* 81-96 (1993). For an application of monopoly theory to the CPA profession, see Robert W. McGee, *Should Only CPAs be Allowed to Audit Financial Statements? An Ethical Look at Monopoly Theory*, *COMMENTARIES ON THE LAW OF ACCOUNTING & FINANCE* (1998).

exam?¹⁶ That way, those who have gained the necessary knowledge through self-study and work experience will be able to serve the public by performing CPA services. What difference does it make *how* CPA candidates have acquired their knowledge as long as they *have* acquired it? Why should competent accountants be prevented from entering the CPA profession just because they may not be able to afford a four-year college education?

THE RIGHTS APPROACH

The arguments given above are all persuasive to some extent. Those who disagree with the position taken in the utilitarian-based arguments summarized above can likely make equally persuasive utilitarian-based arguments of their own that reach the opposite conclusion. In fact, the accounting "establishment," as personified by the AICPA and the National Association of State Boards of Accountancy (NASBA) has done just that.¹⁷ But the fatal flaw in any attempt at utilitarian-based reasoning is that there is no way to precisely measure gains and losses.¹⁸ Utilitarian theory ultimately is grounded in majoritarianism.¹⁹ Yet majoritarianism is utterly irrelevant where

¹⁶ For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Let's Abolish the Education Requirement for Professional Certification: An Analysis from the Perspectives of Law, Economics & Ethics*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Summer 1998).

¹⁷ *AICPA and NASBA Presidents Set the Record Straight on 150-Hour Education Requirement*, 179 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTANCY 19-20 (June 1995). This statement supposedly refutes all the arguments of those who oppose the 150 semester-hour requirement. AICPA and NASBA present "facts" to support their arguments.

¹⁸ MURRAY N. ROTHBARD, *MAN, ECONOMY AND STATE* 260-268 (1970).

¹⁹ It is impossible to measure the extent of the gains and losses that result from the adoption of some policy. Some individuals will be harmed a lot, others will be harmed a little, some will benefit a lot and some will benefit a little. Since it is impossible to quantify "a lot" and "a little," the easy way out of the dilemma is to count heads in an attempt to determine how many winners and losers there are

rights are involved.

No majority, no matter how large, has the moral authority to violate anyone's rights. No moral majority can vote to imprison Japanese-Americans just because they are Japanese. Yet the U.S. government did precisely that during World War II for national security reasons. During the 1930s and 1940s, various religious and ethnic groups were persecuted by the Nazis, perhaps with majority approval. Yet the fact that some majority might approve of the action does not mean that they have the right to engage in such activity. No majority can make something morally right that is morally wrong.

During the first half of the nineteenth century, a large majority of some communities honestly believed that slavery was, on balance, a beneficial institution. Slavery employed thousands of people who would otherwise be unemployed, and perhaps subject to homelessness and starvation. In ancient Roman and Greek times, when most slaves were former members of opposing armies, the argument was made that slavery was a good institution because the alternative was death for the soldiers in the opposing army who had the misfortune to be captured. The idea that slavery can be good is outmoded in modern societies because rights theory has replaced utilitarian theory as far as the question of slavery is concerned.

Rights theory has also been recognized to be superior to utilitarian theory in western political systems to a certain extent. The bill of rights in the U.S. Constitution, for example, guarantees certain basic rights against raw majoritarianism. Freedom of speech, press and religion are some examples that could be cited. These rights are protected by law even if a majority of 99.9 percent of some legislature vote to infringe upon some right.²⁰ Rights

without regard to how much each individual wins or loses. The result is resorting to majoritarianism.

²⁰ Unfortunately, this statement is not as true as it once was. Practically every week some legislature votes to disparage property or contract rights in some way or other. Individuals are no longer completely free to enter into any contract they

theory has also been applied to international trade theory to some extent,²¹ although trade theory continues to be influenced primarily by utilitarianism. There have also been some general treatises on rights theory²² and on comparisons of utilitarianism to rights theory.²³

Before we discuss rights theory, it is first necessary to clarify what rights theory is, and how it must be distinguished from some other concepts. First, we must distinguish between positive and negative rights. An example of positive rights is the right to subsidized housing. The right of a tenant to below-market rent is at the expense of the right of the landlord to rent his property for whatever price he sees fit. The landlord's property right must be violated so that the tenant can have below-market rent.

The "right" to a free education is another positive right. The only way one individual can have a "right" to a free education is if others are forced to pay for it. Those who pay have their property rights disparaged because they are forced to part with some cash in the form of taxes. In order for one person to have this positive right to an education, the negative rights of others (the

want. The Supreme Court in the 1930s decided to ignore the Contract Clause of the U.S. Constitution and contract rights have been eroded ever since.

²¹ Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in NAFTA, GATT and All Other Trade Agreements*, 14 NW J. INT'L L. & BUS. 549-565 (1994); Robert W. McGee, *The Moral Case for Free Trade*, 29 J. WORLD TRADE 69-76 (Feb. 1995); Robert W. McGee, *Some Thoughts on Antidumping Laws: Utilitarianism, Human Rights and the Case for Repeal*, 96 EUROPEAN BUS. REV. 27-33 (No. 5, 1996); Robert W. McGee and Walter Block, *Must Protectionism Always Violate Rights?* 24 INT'L J. SOCIAL ECON. 393-407 (1997); Robert W. McGee and Walter Block, *Ethical Aspects of Initiating Antidumping Actions*, 24 INT'L J. SOCIAL ECON. 599-608 (1997).

²² TIBOR MACHAN, *INDIVIDUALS AND THEIR RIGHTS* (1989); ROBERT NOZICK, *ANARCHY, STATE AND UTOPIA* (1974).

²³ RICHARD B. BRANDT, *MORALITY, UTILITARIANISM, AND RIGHTS* (1992); ALAN GEWIRTH, *HUMAN RIGHTS: ESSAYS ON JUSTIFICATION AND APPLICATIONS* (1982); RUSSELL HARDIN, *MORALITY WITHIN THE LIMITS OF REASON* (1988); ELLEN FRANKEL PAUL, FRED D. MILLER, JR. AND JEFFREY PAUL, EDS., *HUMAN RIGHTS* (1984); J. RICHARD PENNOCK AND JOHN W. CHAPMAN, EDITORS, *ETHICS, ECONOMICS, AND THE LAW* (1982).

right not to have property confiscated, in this case) must be violated.

Another distinctive feature of any positive right is its source. All positive rights come from government. Some government must pass a law to create a positive right that did not previously exist. While positive rights regimes may appear to be zero-sum games -- where winners and losers exactly offset each other -- in fact, they are negative sum games because of enforcement costs. Violating negative rights also adversely affects behavior in ways that tend to retard economic growth. For example, if property rights are disparaged, there is a tendency not to invest, which retards employment growth and economic growth.

Negative rights, on the other hand, are not created by government. Indeed, the reason why governments are created is to protect negative rights, such as the right to life, liberty, property and the right to contract and earn a livelihood. Stated negatively, these rights are the right not to be deprived of life, liberty or property, etc.

Another feature that distinguishes negative rights from positive rights is that negative rights can never conflict. My right to life does not interfere with your right to life. My right to property, free speech or religion, or to earn a livelihood does not interfere with your equal right to do the same. Thus, negative rights are a positive-sum game because there are only winners. Negative rights regimes are therefore superior to positive rights regimes, because under negative rights regimes, no one's rights are violated. In any positive rights regime, however, one person's "rights" can be created only at the expense of another's rights.

One argument that has been put forth to counter this nonconflicting attribute of negative rights regimes is the concept of "harm." The argument goes something like this. If a supermarket opens up across the street from a small, mom and pop grocery store, mom and pop are likely to be harmed. Therefore, there is no absolute right to open a supermarket across the street from mom and pop.

The flaw in this line of reasoning is due to a confusion in

the relationship between harmful conduct and conduct that violates rights. True, mom and pop stand to be harmed if a supermarket opens across the street from them. They will likely lose business if a competitor within their market area offers a wider selection at lower prices. But it does not follow that their rights are violated, because mom and pop have no inherent claim on the income of consumers. If consumers choose to do business with the supermarket, they have every right to do so. To prevent consumers from having this choice -- which would happen if some government prevented the supermarket from opening -- would be to violate the rights of the consumers who would otherwise benefit by having a supermarket in their neighborhood, not to mention the supermarket owners, who cannot enter into acts of voluntary exchange because of the decision.

Now that these definitions and confusions have been clarified, let's apply negative rights theory to the 150 semester-hour requirement. In a negative rights regime, labor is owned by individuals, who can give or sell it to others. The right to contract, which involves the right to enter into voluntary, non-rights-violating exchanges with others, is violated if some other individual or group of individuals (usually government) prevents, by force or the threat of force, individuals from offering their services to others under voluntary, mutually agreeable terms.

The 150 semester-hour requirement violates rights because it acts as a barrier to market entry.²⁴ It prevents individuals from

²⁴ Raising barriers to market entry by law violates rights because it prevents individuals from offering the fruits of their labor to interested parties. It prevents them from working, which is a basic human right, and it prevents them from entering into contracts. Utilitarians could also support the view that the requirement acts as a barrier to market entry, but they would say that the 150 semester hour requirement is bad policy because it decreases efficiency and results in suboptimization.

It should be pointed out that not all barriers to market entry violate rights. For example, your rights are not violated if you want to start an auto company but you don't have the several billion dollars needed to get started. But rights are violated if some government prevents you from entering into contracts and trading the property you have for the property you want.

offering their CPA services because it prevents them from becoming CPAs in the first place. One might argue that the 150 semester-hour "law" -- that's what it is, a law -- is in the public interest because it prevents less qualified people from offering their services to the public.²⁵ Many arguments could be made to defend or dismantle this position.²⁶ These arguments are defective, however, because they are utilitarian-based.

When it comes to the right to enter into voluntary exchange and offer your labor, majoritarian arguments -- such as any utilitarian argument -- are irrelevant. No majority can morally prohibit consenting adults from entering into voluntary exchanges.²⁷ Preventing such activities from occurring is an abuse of government power. The only legitimate functions of government are to protect basic negative rights, such as the rights to life, liberty, property and contract. To the extent that government goes beyond these functions, it is acting illegitimately.²⁸ Raising the cost of market entry by the use of force -- government is force -- is morally reprehensible. The 150-hour requirement will raise barriers to entry that are so high that many potential accountants will choose not to pay.

²⁵ The AICPA, NASBA and various other groups have been advocating the adoption of a uniform accountancy law in each state to make the practice of public accounting more uniform.

²⁶ Similar arguments have been made with regard to occupational licensure laws for other professions. For some discussions on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *Occupational Licensure Laws: An Economic and Ethical Approach*, COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS (1998); Robert W. McGee, *Let's Abolish Licensure Laws for Accountants: An Analysis from the Perspectives of Law, Economics & Ethics*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Summer 1998).

²⁷ That is not to say that majorities need to approve conduct that is perhaps reprehensible. It is just that no one, whether a majority of 99 percent or a minority of one, has any moral right to use force or the threat of force to prevent consenting adults from doing whatever they like as long as no one's rights are violated.

²⁸ FREDERIC BASTIAT, THE LAW 21-29 (1968), first published in French as LA LOI and reprinted many times.

If one begins with the premise that there should be such a thing as a CPA certificate -- let's assume so for the sake of argument -- then there is only one policy one may adopt that is non-rights-violating. Individuals who want to take the CPA exam should be allowed to do so without restrictions. Abolish all education requirements.

Requiring a college degree -- which consists of 50% liberal arts courses and 25% other nonaccounting courses -- acts as a very high barrier to entry, thus depriving people of their right to earn a livelihood. Those who don't have a solid background in accounting won't be able to pass the exam whether they have a college degree or not. Those who do have the knowledge will be able to pass the exam and earn a livelihood as a CPA whether they have a college degree or not. The public interest, if there is one, will be just as well protected by this policy as by the present policy of requiring four or five years of college.

This competency-based approach is not new. The University of London has been awarding degrees using this approach since the mid-nineteenth century. Students who want to earn a degree at the University of London can do so by enrolling in a degree program, studying on their own from anywhere in the world, and taking exams at specified times.

Those who decide to prepare for the CPA exam by taking just accounting courses in college could cut the cost of becoming a CPA by 75%, since they would need to take just 30 semester hours or so of courses. Those who decide to study on their own, and those who have acquired their knowledge through work experience and independent study, could save even more. The University of London approach could easily be adopted as an inexpensive, non-rights-violating way for individuals to become CPAs.

It is always wrong to use force, or the threat of force, to deprive someone of a livelihood, no matter how noble the intent. Those who advocate that a mandatory education requirement²⁹ be

²⁹ The mandatory education requirement does not stop when one passes the CPA exam. Many states and some foreign countries requirement continuing

met before individuals can hold themselves out to the public as CPAs fail to even address this crucial issue.

professional education in order to keep the license to practice. For the ethics of such a mandatory continuing education requirement, see Robert W. McGee, *The Ethics of Mandatory Continuing Professional Education: A Look at the IFAC Model*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Summer 1998).